

Motion Word Problems

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Abstract: While solving these sums it is necessary to remember that by uniform motion travel is connected with speed v and time t in proportion $s=vt$, the same proportion is right if it is considered average speed of way by irregular motion.

Examples of word problem solutions using two methods

1. A cyclist left the point A heading to point B. After 3 hours, the cyclist was followed by a tourist on a moped, whose speed was 20% higher than the speed of the cyclist. After a while, a motorcyclist, whose speed was 50% faster than the speed of the moped, rode from A to B. How many hours after the cyclist's departure did the A to B rider leave if all three arrived in B simultaneously?

Solution:

1st method is algebraic:

The speed of the cyclist is denoted for x km/h, and the speed of the tourist on the moped - $1.2x$ km/h, the speed of the rider - $1.8x$ km/h.

Let the distance $AV=S$ km, and t hours after the tourist, motorcyclist rode on a moped and spent the whole way $\frac{S}{1.8x}$ hours, then

$$\left(t + \frac{S}{1.8x}\right) \cdot 1.2x = \left(t + \frac{S}{1.8x} + 3\right) \cdot x$$

Let's Divide the two parts of the equality by x ,

$$\text{we will receive } \left(t + \frac{S}{1.8x}\right) \cdot 1.2 - \left(t + \frac{S}{1.8x}\right) = 3$$

$$\left(t + \frac{S}{1.8x}\right) \cdot 0.2 = 3, t + \frac{S}{1.8x} = 15, \left(t + \frac{S}{1.8x}\right) \cdot 1.2x = S, 15 \cdot 1.2x = S, S = 18x$$

$$\frac{S}{1.8x} = 10, t + 10 = 15, t = 5$$

Answer: Eight hours after the cyclist's departure, a motorcyclist arrived from A to B.

2nd method – geometric

$$\begin{cases} \frac{S}{T-3} = 1,2 \cdot \frac{S}{T} & (1) \\ \frac{S}{T-t-3} = 1,8 \cdot \frac{S}{T} & (2) \end{cases}$$

(1) → TS=1,2TS-3,6S

3,6S=0,2TS

T=18

(2) → $\frac{S}{15-t} = \frac{S}{10}$, $10S = 15S - tS$, $tS = 5S$, $t=5$

Answer: Eight hours after the cyclist’s departure, a motorcyclist arrived from A to B.

2. Two cyclists left point A to reach point B at the same time. In 4 hours the first cyclist fell behind the second at the 2/5 of distance between A and B. What time is needed for the first cyclist to cross the distance between A and B, if the time needed for the second cyclist is 1 h 40 m less?

Solution:

1st method, algebraic:

Let’s denote the speed of the first cyclist as x km/h, then the speed of the second is y km/h. If distance AB= S, then:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{S}{x} = \frac{S}{y} + 1\frac{2}{3} \\ 4(y - x) = \frac{2S}{5} \end{cases}$$

Let’s find $\frac{S}{x}$

$$y = \frac{S}{10} + x, \frac{S}{x} = \frac{S}{\frac{S}{10} + x} + 1\frac{2}{3}, \frac{S}{x} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{x}{S}} + \frac{5}{3}, \frac{S}{x} = t, , t = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{t}} + \frac{5}{3}, t = \frac{t}{0,1t+1} + \frac{5}{3}$$

3(0,1t + 1) ≠ 0

3t(0,1t+1)=3t+5(0,1t+1), 0,3t²-0,5t-5=0, t=5

Answer: the first cyclist will pass the distance from A to B in 5 hours.

2nd method – geometric:

Based on the similarity of triangles rules: ACD and AEF $\frac{S}{t} = \frac{x}{4}$, $x = \frac{4S}{t}$ km

Based on the similarity of triangles rules: AGD and AHI : $\frac{x + \frac{2S}{5}}{4} = \frac{S}{t - \frac{5}{3}}$

$$\frac{\frac{4S}{t} + \frac{2S}{5}}{4} = \frac{3S}{3t-5}, \frac{t+10}{10t} = \frac{3}{3t-5}, 3t^2 - 5t - 50 = 0, t = 5$$

Answer: the first cyclist will pass the distance from A to B in 5 hours.

3. A driver leaves point A to reach point B. A biker leaves point B towards him after an hour. Another hour later the distance between them made up $\frac{5}{9}$ of the distance from A to B. how many hours are needed for the biker to pass the distance from A to B.

Solution:

1st method, algebraic:

Let's denote the distance between A and B as S , the speed of the driver as x km/h, the speed of the biker as y km/h, then according to the word problem $2x + y = \frac{4}{9}S$ and $\frac{S}{x} - \frac{S}{y} = 3$. Let's make up a simultaneous equation and find the time it takes for the biker to pass the distance from A to B, i.e. $\frac{S}{y}$

$$\begin{cases} S = \frac{9}{4}(2x + y) & (1) \\ \frac{\frac{9}{4}(2x + y)}{y} - \frac{\frac{9}{4}(2x + y)}{x} = 3 & (2) \end{cases}$$

From the equation (2) we get $\frac{9}{2} \cdot \frac{x}{y} + \frac{9}{4} - \frac{9}{2} - \frac{9}{4} \cdot \frac{y}{x} = 3$,

$$6 \cdot \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^2 - 7 \cdot \frac{x}{y} - 3 = 0, \frac{x}{y} = 1,5.$$

Equation (1) follows that $\frac{S}{y} = \frac{9}{4} \cdot \left(2 \cdot \frac{x}{y} + 1\right) = 9$

Answer: the biker passes the distance from A to B in 9 hours

2nd method – geometric:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{4}{9}S - x = \frac{5}{9}S + x & (1) \\ \frac{S - x}{t - 2} = \frac{x}{2} & (2) \end{cases}$$

(2) suggests that $2S - 2x = tx - 2x$, $x = \frac{2S}{t}$

(1) suggests that $(\frac{4S}{9} - \frac{2S}{t})(t + 2) = \frac{5S}{9} + \frac{2S}{t}$, let's multiply both parts of the equation by $\frac{9t}{S}$

$$(4t - 18)(t + 2) = 5t + 18,$$

$$4t^2 - 10t - 36 - 5t - 18 = 0,$$

$$4t^2 - 15t - 54 = 0,$$

$$t = 6$$

Answer: the biker will pass the distance from A to B in 6+3=9 hours.

4. The second car is catching up with the first one, which is at the certain point of distance S. The time after which second car catches up with the first is 1,5 hours more than the time it takes for the first car to pass the distance S, and is 2 hours more than the time it takes for the second car to pass this distance. Find how much time it takes for second car to catch up with the first.

Solution:

1st method, algebraic:

Let the speed of 1st car be x km/h, while the speed of 2nd one - y km/h.

$$1) \frac{S}{x} = t_1, (\frac{S}{x} + 1,5)y = AC, BC = AC - AB = (\frac{S}{x} + 1,5)y - S,$$

$$2) \frac{S}{y} = t_2, (\frac{S}{y} + 1,5)y = AC, \frac{S}{x} + 1,5 = \frac{S}{y} + 2, \frac{S(y-x)}{xy} = 0,5; t_1 - t_2 = 0,5$$

$$\frac{S+U}{y} - 1,5 = \frac{S}{x}, \frac{S+U}{y} - 2 = \frac{S}{y}$$

$$\frac{S+U}{y} = \frac{U}{x}, Sx + Ux = Uy, Sx = U(y - x), U = \frac{Sx}{y-x}$$

$$\frac{S + \frac{Sx}{y-x}}{y} - 1,5 = \frac{S}{x}, \frac{Sy}{y(y-x)} - 1,5 = \frac{S}{x}, \frac{S}{y-x} - 1,5 = \frac{S}{x}, \frac{S(2x-y)}{x(y-x)} = 1,5$$

$$\frac{S + \frac{Sx}{y-x}}{y} - 2 = \frac{S}{y}, \frac{Sy}{y(y-x)} - 2 = \frac{S}{y}, \frac{Sx}{y(y-x)} = 2$$

$$\frac{Sx}{y(y-x)} \cdot \frac{x(y-x)}{S(2x-y)} = \frac{4}{3}, 3x^2 = 4y(2x - y), 3x^2 - 8yx + 4y^2 = 0$$

$$(3x - 2y)(x - 2y) = 0$$

$$x_1 = 2y, x_2 = \frac{2}{3}y$$

$$y = \frac{3}{2}x, \frac{Sx}{\frac{3}{2}x^2} = 0,5, \frac{S}{x} = 1,5$$

Answer: the 2nd car will catch up with the 1st one within 3 hours.

2nd method – geometric:

$$\frac{x}{2} = \frac{S}{t-2}, x = \frac{2S}{t-2}$$

$$\frac{S+x}{2t-1,5} = \frac{S}{t-1,5}, \frac{S + \frac{2S}{t-2}}{2t-1,5} = \frac{S}{t-1,5}, \frac{2+t-2}{t-2} = \frac{1}{t-1,5}, \frac{t}{(t-2)(2t-1,5)} = \frac{1}{t-1,5}$$

$$t^2 - 1,5t = 2t^2 - 1,5t - 4t + 3, t^2 - 4t + 3 = 0$$

$$t = 3.$$

Answer: the 2nd car will catch up with the 1st one within 3 hours.